

Supplementary table 6 Associations between different ACPA fine-specificities and HLA-DRB1 SE, in anti-CCP2-positive and anti-CCP2-negative RA

Subgroup		OR (95% CI) ^a		P-value ^b
		CCP2-	CCP2+	
Cit-Fib β_{60-74}	neg	1.0 (0.8-1.2)	3.8 (2.5-4.6)	0.0007
	pos	2.2 (1.4-3.7)	6.0 (5.0-7.2)	
Cit-Peptide-5	neg	1.0 (0.9-1.2)	4.0 (3.0-5.4)	0.04
	pos	1.5 (0.9-2.4)	5.8 (4.8-7.0)	
Cit-Peptide-Z1	neg	1.0 (0.9-1.2)	3.3 (2.6-4.2)	<0.0001
	pos	1.5 (0.8-2.8)	7.0 (5.5-8.4)	
Cit-Fib β_{36-52}	neg	1.0 (0.9-1.3)	5.8 (4.4-7.7)	0.4
	pos	1.0 (0.5-1.9)	5.1 (4.2-6.2)	
Cit-Vim $_{60-75}$	neg	1.0 (0.9-1.2)	3.1 (2.5-3.9)	<0.0001
	pos	2.8 (1.1-7.0)	7.9 (6.3-10.0)	
CEP-1	neg	1.0 (0.9-1.2)	3.4 (2.7-4.2)	<0.0001
	pos	1.8 (0.9-3.7)	7.7 (6.1-9.7)	
cfc1-cyc	neg	1.1 (0.9-1.3)	5.9 (4.6-7.7)	0.2
	pos	0.9 (0.4-2.1)	5.0 (4.1-6.1)	
Cit-Fib $\alpha_{563-583}$	neg	1.1 (0.9-1.2)	4.5 (3.5-5.6)	0.06
	pos	1.3 (0.5-3.3)	6.0 (4.9-7.5)	
Cit-Peptide-Z2	neg	1.1 (0.9-1.2)	4.7 (3.8-5.9)	0.2
	pos	1.5 (0.6-3.4)	5.9 (4.7-7.5)	
Cit-Peptide-1	neg	1.1 (0.9-1.2)	4.7 (3.9-5.8)	0.07
	pos	1.3 (0.7-2.4)	6.1 (4.8-7.8)	
Cit-Fib $\alpha_{621-635}$	neg	1.0 (0.9-1.2)	4.9 (4.0-6.0)	0.3
	pos	1.5 (0.8-2.9)	5.9 (4.6-7.5)	
Cit-Peptide-Bla26	neg	1.1 (0.9-1.3)	4.7 (3.9-5.8)	0.1
	pos	0.6 (0.3-1.2)	6.3 (4.9-8.2)	
Cit-Vim $_{2-17}$	neg	1.1 (0.9-1.2)	4.4 (3.6-5.4)	0.007
	pos	1.3 (0.6-3.1)	7.1 (5.4-9.2)	
Cit-F4 _(Cit-Cit)	neg	1.0 (0.9-1.3)	5.7 (4.6-7.0)	0.2
	pos	0.8 (0.4-1.7)	4.8 (3.7-6.1)	
Cit-F4 _(R-Cit)	neg	1.1 (0.9-1.2)	5.2 (4.3-6.3)	0.8
	pos	1.3 (0.5-3.7)	5.6 (4.2-7.4)	
Cit-Fib $\alpha_{580-600}$	neg	1.1 (0.9-1.2)	4.8 (4.0-5.8)	0.06
	pos	1.4 (0.6-3.3)	7.2 (5.1-10.1)	
Cit-Fib α_{36-50}	neg	1.1 (0.9-1.3)	5.5 (4.6-6.7)	0.2
	pos	0.9 (0.4-1.9)	4.4 (3.1-6.1)	
Cit-C1	neg	1.1 (0.9-1.2)	5.2 (4.4-6.2)	0.6
	pos	2.2 (0.7-7.2)	5.9 (3.7-9.3)	
Cit-F4 _(Cit-R)	neg	1.1 (0.9-1.2)	5.8 (4.9-6.9)	<0.0001
	pos	2.3 (0.8-6.5)	2.1 (1.4-3.4)	

^a Odds ratios (OR) were adjusted for age, gender and residential area. Significant ORs are shown in bold. ^b P-values indicate differences in ORs between ACPA fine-specificity-positive and -negative subsets, in anti-CCP2-positive RA.